

DEMOCRATIZATION OF MANAGEMENT AND THE CHALLENGES OF IMPLEMENTING IT IN STATE PUBLIC SCHOOLS IN CEARÁ

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ABSTRACT

The period of the history of Brazilian education, the issue of Democratic Management was as important throughout government initiatives as it was in recent decades. The 1988 Constitution

of the Federative Republic of Brazil established the democratic management of education as one of the seven principles necessary to manage public schools, referring us to the importance of educational policies. That said, this work aims to identify the challenges encountered in the implementation of the democratization of management in a school unit in Crateús/CE, through a broad investigation in a critical perspective (FREIRE, 2007), characterized by the nature and scope of the unit of study in question. From an interview with members of the school community, we observed the existence of mechanisms that promote democracy, granting greater autonomy in the development of academic activities.

Keywords: Democracy; Public Management; Education in the State of Ceará.

1. DEMOCRACY: GUIDING IDEAS FOR OUR REFLECTION

Democracy is a concept that can present multiple meanings from different perspectives and, in this context, the democratic participation of citizens is one of the greatest social advances achieved, affecting the ability to intervene in the political and social life of the community in which they are inserted, manifesting itself in the implementation of more democratic and egalitarian societies (DELVAL, 2007).

The principles of democratization and decentralization of public management, endorsed by the State Legislative Assembly of Ceará, provide for the choice of school directors through a selection process and direct elections (CEARÁ, 2003), characterized by the valorization of public education.

In this process, we come across aspects such as the importance of leadership in promoting assertive actions that can positively impact the school environment, as through this, organizations create more opportunities through the adequate performance of complex tasks.

In this sense, a democratic education equips citizens, enabling them to make choices in the face of society's demands (UNESCO, 2016). Recognizing the school as a space for the transformation and implementation of culture and politics, impacts on aspects such as intellectual autonomy, student protagonism and ethical-scientific production, providing a space that is characterized by diversity, construction and socialization of knowledge.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research is based on the perspective of Paulo Freire's critical and liberating pedagogy, an educational theory developed from theoretical and epistemological arguments that highlight the empirical field, seeking to analyze the truths about social and cultural reproduction that affect society (FREIRE, 2007). The research subjects were representatives of

a state public school located in the municipality of Crateús/CE, characterized as a case study which, according to Triviños (1987, p. 133), “is a research category whose object is a unit that is analyzed in depth and whose characteristics are determined by the nature and scope, giving the researcher support in the investigation process”.

The research presents a qualitative approach that is understood as one that deals with the subjective level of social reality, treated through the history, values and attitudes of social actors (MINAYO, 2013). As for the research technique, interviews were used, giving the researcher the opportunity to formulate questions with the aim of obtaining data about the field of investigation, characterized as an asymmetrical dialogue, as one party seeks to collect data and the other acts as a source. information (GIL, 1987). Thus, the principal, a student, a teacher, a mother and an employee participated in the interview and, among the topics covered, we have: 1) Participation mechanisms existing at the school; 2) Form of participation of agents who are part of the school; 3) Management experienced by the school; 4) School management priorities; 5) School management, the pedagogical work carried out in the classroom and the autonomy of the school; 6) School regulations; 7) Method of choosing the school director. Next, the analyzes of the proposed interview will be presented with the appropriate considerations.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS AND ITS ANALYSIS

In this section, the responses from the different segments of the proposed interview are analyzed. Regarding the topic *Participation mechanisms existing at the school*, all segments surveyed (principal, student, teacher, mother and employee) responded that the participation mechanisms existing at the school are the school council, the student union and the teachers' congregation. About the *form of participation of the agents that make up the school*, according to the school director, the employee and the teacher, the members of the various collegial bodies existing in the school participate when deciding on the “life of the school”, with systematized meetings. Regarding the *Management that the school experiences*, the research reveals that the management of the school space is characterized as participatory, democratic and committed to the training of the different segments, enabling shared decision-making, guaranteeing the quality of the services provided.

With regard to *School Management Priorities*, according to the teacher, priorities are discussed by the collegiate, mainly in school council meetings, being considered a positive aspect, enabling a test of democracy and participation for agents in the teaching and learning

process. . Another aspect highlighted is the appreciation of educators through care and welcoming moments.

Regarding the relationship between *school management and the pedagogical work carried out in the classroom* , all segments stated that the work carried out by the school is excellent, always open for discussion, contributing to the student's education. One of the factors that constitutes a challenge is the lack of qualified teachers in Natural Sciences and Mathematics. The importance of interdisciplinary and contextualized work is highlighted, which according to Lima and Alves (2022), promotes intellectual autonomy and student protagonism in facing the problems of the 21st century.

Next, he was asked about the *school's autonomy* in decision-making. The various segments stated that it has autonomy, which is expressed in the clarity of how situations are handled, seeking to achieve the objectives set by the board. Counting on everyone's support and collaboration is essential to achieving excellent results. Autonomy does not constitute absolute freedom, as freedom occurs in relation to the construction process in which one is inserted.

When it comes to the *school rules*, it was drawn up based on studies and debates with the participation of all segments of the school community. About the *form Choosing the school director* follows the stages of the public competition, followed by the direct election process. Everyone considers the process to be democratic, enabling greater interaction between the chosen director and the school community, promoting greater interaction with the student union, school council, group of teachers and parents and/or guardians.

4. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

We verified, through the research findings, the existence of mechanisms that promote democratic management. For a school to function, it needs to comply with legal aspects and the bodies that administer education, favoring coexistence in order to provide opportunities for democratic exercise, as well as providing a favorable environment for the development of academic activities.

The position of school director presupposes sensitivity to deal with conflict, making use of socio-emotional skills, respecting differences, overcoming limitations, harmonizing, positively leading the group in order to consolidate the project within the community. Therefore, democratic management requires community participation in the actions developed, articulating interests, feelings and values.

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